

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

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ABSTRACT: Caring for the business environment among young people is one of the commitments of the @okoce.indonesia account, and through various posts, behavioral changes have occurred. Inviting the younger generation to care about the business environment and Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). This study aims to determine the magnitude of the influence of social media usage and information quality on changes in environmental care behavior among businesses and MSMEs. This research uses the Uses and Gratification Theory. The research uses a quantitative approach, reinforced by qualitative methods, with an explanatory research nature and a survey research method. Data processing results for correlation show a moderate relationship between social media usage and behavior change at 0.499, a moderate relationship between information quality and behavior change at 0.503, and a moderate simultaneous relationship between social media usage and information quality and behavior change at 0.479. The F-test results indicate a positive and significant influence of social media usage and information quality on behavior change.

KEYWORDS: Social Media Usage; Information Quality; Behavior Change; Uses and Gratification Theory; Instagram Media.

INTRODUCTION

Online media is one form of advancement in information and communication technology that can be enjoyed anywhere and anytime (Oisina, 2020). One example of an online media application is social media (Mulawarman & Nurfitri, 2017). The presence of social media and the growing number of users day by day provide an interesting fact about the power of the internet in people's lives. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram, and Path are some of the social media platforms that are popular with many people (Nasrullah, 2015). Social media is intended as a platform for its users to easily participate, share, and exchange information and ideas within virtual communities and networks (Yuni Fitriani, 2017).

With the various advancements available, social media helps meet the information needs of society. Social media is a digital platform that provides users with various interesting features accessible at any time (Febrina et al., 2024). The use of social media has become a necessity for obtaining educational information and showing concern for the business environment. One of the most widely used social media platforms is Instagram. The variety of content available makes people feel comfortable using the application, from business and education to product reviews and more. Instagram, as an application, quickly delivers information in the form of photos and shares it to other social networks (Febrina et al., 2024). Instagram has many interesting features that can satisfy its users. With Instagram, users can communicate and interact through the Like, Comment, and Direct Message features. On Instagram, users can follow each other, and once followed, a user's activity can be seen through their uploads by other users (Febrina et al., 2024). Instagram is an application for quickly sending information, namely in the form of photos, and sharing it on other social networks. This research uses the @okoce.indonesia account, which is active in sharing information about environmental awareness and business.

Various forms of quality information are delivered through Instagram with the aim of educating the public. It is important to consider when communicating or disseminating information through social media (Yuni Fitriani, 2017), in order to create interest among young people to actively participate in various activities related to the business environment, especially Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The quality of information in posts will be an attraction and can create a good impression, encouraging the public, especially young people, to actively participate in protecting the environment and also in business, especially MSMEs. Information quality is a measure of how clear the information and knowledge are presented or conveyed to the public. However, when using social media, the quality of information received by users can influence public behavior regarding environmental care in business, especially for MSMEs targeting young people.

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

Muzdalifah Ar'robby et al.'s research encourages Generation Z to use Instagram as a platform for spreading positive messages and promoting positive social change, such as environmental campaigns, businesses, or other social movements, which would be a positive step (Muzdalifah Ar'robby et al., 2025). Research by Febrina, Salamah, and Sakina states: The quality of information on social media is influenced by several factors, namely: accuracy, novelty, relevance, diversity, and credibility of the information presented (Febrina et al., 2024).

The above phenomenon shows that the interesting posts shared by @okeoce.indonesia to educate followers, especially young people, through this research, aims to determine whether high-quality educational posts can influence young people to become interested in the business environment, especially MSMEs. The objectives of this study are: to determine the magnitude of the influence of using Instagram media and Information Quality on Changes in Business Environmental Care Behavior (Survey on the @okeoce.indonesia Account).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Uses and Gratifications Theory

In this study, the researcher used the Uses and Gratifications Theory because it was considered relevant to explain how audiences actively choose media they believe can meet specific needs and provide certain satisfactions. Through this approach, researchers observed that consumers utilize the social media platform Instagram to seek information. The use of social media plays a role in influencing behavioral change. The theory used in this study is the Uses and Gratifications theory. Blumler and Katz stated that media users are active in selecting and using media. Media users are active participants in the communication process. Media users seek the best media sources for their needs. According to this theory, media consumers have the freedom to choose how (through media) they use media and what media will become, influencing them. This theory also claims that media can do things that negatively impact life. This does not affect your behavior or your choice of events you want to watch (Child, J. T., & Haridakis, 2018 in (Febrina et al., 2024)).

The development of information and communication technology has now been realized in the form of an artificial intelligence device called a smartphone, and this discovery has brought about changes in all aspects of life. The availability of internet connections and smartphones has accelerated the digital communication era, making these devices a primary need for most of the world's population. The existence of social media through smartphones with their advanced features has become an effective means of disseminating and receiving information, which is utilized by every layer of society, from official institutions, both governmental and private, communities, organizations, and individuals in the wider community (Kurniawan, 2020).

Variable X1: Social Media Usage. According to research by Hauer (Solis, 2011), there are four dimensions of social media usage, which are used as dimensions in this study:

1. Context "How we frame our stories" - how to shape a message or story (information);
2. Communication "The practice of sharing our story as well as listening, responding, and growing" - how to share a story or information, including how to listen, respond, and grow;
3. Collaboration "Working together to make things better and more efficient and effective" - cooperation between social media users to make good things more effective and efficient;
4. Connection "The relationships we forge and maintain" - maintaining established relationships.

As for the variable X2: Information Quality, according to Mulyanto (2009), information quality has dimensions, namely:

1. Information must be accurate, meaning it is not biased or misleading, free from errors, and clearly reflects its purpose;
2. Information must be timely. Information produced should not arrive late (obsolete) to be of good value, as information is the basis for decision-making;
3. Information must be relevant. Information is considered high quality if it is relevant to the user. This information must be useful to the user. The relevance of information for each person differs from one another.

In the context of psychology, there are several dimensions of individual behavior, including (Andersen, 2023):

1. Cognitive Change, to explain all mental activities related to perception, thought, memory, and information processing that enable a person to acquire knowledge, solve problems, and plan for the future, or all psychological processes related to how individuals learn, pay attention, observe, imagine, estimate, evaluate, and think about their environment (Amir & Priatna, 2018);
2. Emotional Changes: According to the traditional school of thought pioneered by G. Stanley Hall, these changes are primarily caused by changes occurring in hormonal glands. Indicators in this dimension include changes in emotional expression, stress levels, or an individual's emotional well-being when facing specific situations (Gali & Ananda, 2022).
3. Psychomotor Changes: These relate to behavior in the form of motor skills (Arifin et al., 2017).

In this study, the research hypotheses include:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of Social Media Usage on Changes in Business Environmental Care Behavior;
2. There is a positive and significant influence of Information Quality on Changes in Business Environmental Care Behavior;

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

- There is a positive and significant influence of Social Media Usage and Information Quality on Changes in Business Environmental Care Behavior.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The approach in this study uses a mixed method where the quantitative approach is strengthened by the qualitative approach. The nature of the research is explanatory and the research method used is a survey. Data collection techniques using questionnaires, interviews, and literature studies. The population in this study consists of 80,500 followers of the @okoce.indonesia account as of November 4, 2025. The research sample was determined using Slovin's formula with an e value of 10%, resulting in 99,512 respondents, rounded up to 100. The sampling technique used was simple random sampling, focusing on followers who actively interacted with the account and had liked or commented on its posts. This research uses a pretest on 30 respondents, with validity and reliability tests. Assuming classical assumptions with data normality tests, correlation tests, multiple correlation tests, multiple regression tests, hypothesis tests using T-tests and F-tests.

Pretest

Validity Test

From the trial with 30 respondents, a validity test was conducted on 8 statement items for the Social Media Usage variable, and the following results were obtained:

Table 1: Validity Test Results
Variable X1: Social Media Usage

Statement	Calculated-r Value	Sign	Calculated r-Table	Explanation
P1	0.579	>	0,361	Valid
P2	0.443	>		Valid
P3	0,470	>		Valid
P4	0.583	>		Valid
P5	0.453	>		Valid
P6	0,487	>		Valid
P7	0.542	>		Valid
P8	0.624	>		Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS for variable X1: Social Media Usage, it can be seen that out of the 8 questionnaire items from the 4 dimensions within the Social Media Usage variable, the statements were given to 30 respondents for the pretest, and the overall results showed that the statements were valid because the calculated r value was greater than the table r value with a significance level of 5% and n = 30, and the table r value was 0.361.

Table 2: Validity Test Results
Variable X2: Information Quality

Statement	Calculated-r Value	Sign	Calculated r-Table	Explanation
P1	0.563	>	0,361	Valid
P2	0.467	>		Valid
P3	0.521	>		Valid
P4	0.663	>		Valid
P5	0.646	>		Valid
P6	0.477	>		Valid
P7	0.680	>		Valid
P8	0.581	>		Valid
P9	0.436	>		Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS for variable X2: Information Quality, it can be seen that out of the 9 questionnaire items from 3 dimensions within the Information Quality variable, the statements given to the 30 respondents for the pretest were all valid, as the calculated r value was greater than the table r value with a significance level of 5% and n = 30, and the table r value was 0.361.

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

Table 3: Validity Test Results

Variable Y: Behavior Change

Statement	Calculated-r Value	Sign	Calculated r-Table	Explanation
P1	0.427	>	0,361	Valid
P2	0.512	>		Valid
P3	0.555	>		Valid
P4	0.639	>		Valid
P5	0.483	>		Valid
P6	0.564	>		Valid
P7	0.582	>		Valid
P8	0.645	>		Valid
P9	0.519	>		Valid

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS for variable Y: Behavior Change, it can be seen that out of the 9 questionnaire items from 3 dimensions in the social media usage variable, the statements given to 30 respondents for the pretest yielded overall valid results, as the calculated r value is greater than the table r value with a significance level of 5% and n = 30, and the table r value is 0.361.

Reliability Test

Reliability Statistics

Table 4: Reliability Test Results

Variable X1: Social Media Usage

Cronbach'sAlpha	N of Items
0.726	8

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS, the variable X1: Social Media Usage has a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.726, which means the Social Media Usage variable is reliable because it yields a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60, with a result of 0.726 > 0.60.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable X2: Information Quality

Cronbach'sAlpha	N of Items
0.777	9

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS, the variable X2: Information Quality has a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.777, which means the Information Quality variable is reliable because it provides a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.60, with a result of 0.777 > 0.60.

Table 6: Reliability Test Results

Variable Y: Behavior Change

Cronbach'sAlpha	N of Items
0.751	9

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

Based on the data processing results obtained using SPSS, variable Y: Purchase Interest has a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.851, which means the information quality variable is reliable because it yields a Cronbach's Alpha value of > 0.60 , with a result of $0.751 > 0.60$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics The characteristics of the respondents in this study are as follows: a. Gender: The respondents in this study consist of 63% male (63 respondents) and 37% female (37 respondents). b. The age of the respondents is dominated by the 21-30 age group, accounting for 43% or 43 respondents. The 31-40 age group accounts for 30% or 30 respondents. The <20 age group accounts for 25% or 25 respondents, and the over 41 age group accounts for 2% or 2 respondents. c. The educational status of the respondents is dominated by Bachelor's and Postgraduate graduates, accounting for 40% or 40 respondents. D3 and S1 students account for 38% or 38 respondents, and 22% or 22 respondents have a high school diploma or equivalent.

Simple Correlation Test

In this study, the simple correlation test is a form of data analysis used to determine or measure the strength and direction of the relationship between two or more variables, as well as to determine the magnitude of the influence caused by the use of social media and information quality on changes in environmental and business-friendly behavior.

Table 7: Results of Simple Correlation Test

Correlations		X1	X2	Y
X1: Penggunaan Media	Pearson Correlation	1	.635**	.499*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0,000	0,000
	N	100	100	100
X2: Kualitas Informasi	Pearson Correlation	.635**	1	.503**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0,000		0,000
	N	100	100	100
Y: Perubahan Perilaku	Pearson Correlation	.499**	.503**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0,000	0,000	
	N	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Here are the results of the reliability test for variable X1: Instagram Media Usage, X2: Information Quality, and Y: Behavior Change:

- Results of the correlation test for variable X1: Instagram Media Usage against Y: Behavior Change, There is a relationship between variable X1: Instagram Media Usage and Y: Behavior Change, this can be seen from the Sig value which is 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The relationship between the two variables is positive; if there is an increase in the Social Media Usage variable, behavior change will also increase. The Pearson correlation coefficient value is 0.699. The relationship between the two variables falls within the strong and positive correlation range because it is within the 0.40-0.599 interval, which indicates a moderate level of relationship;
- Correlation test results for variable X2: Information Quality and variable Y: Attitude Change: There is a relationship between variable X2: Information Quality and Y: Attitude Change. This can be seen from the Sig value, which is 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The relationship between the two variables is positive, meaning that if there is an increase in the information quality variable, the Behavior Change variable will also increase. The Pearson correlation coefficient value is 0.503. The level of relationship between the two variables falls within a positive and strong correlation because it is within the 0.40-0.599 interval, indicating a moderate level of relationship.

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

From the correlation test results above, there is a moderate relationship between social media usage and behavioral change. This is consistent with the interview results conducted with Informant 1, who stated: "The use of the Instagram social media account @okoce.indonesia provides information about caring for the business environment, encouraging the public to care about the business environment, especially MSMEs. Every post shared provides information about the business environment, whether online or onsite. These posts broaden followers' horizons to become aware of and care about business and join MSMEs, as young people are often not concerned with business."

From the simple correlation test results above for the variable Social Media Usage with the dimension of Collaboration "Working together to make things better and more efficient and effective," which is cooperation between social media users to make good things more effective and efficient, is an activity often carried out by the @okoce.indonesia account with other communities. This is done to share information, such as with the #bisnis #UMKM community, to continue collaborating with other parties, inviting the public, especially young people, to care about the business environment and MSMEs. This is evident from various posts shared thru stories and reels.

From the correlation test results above, there is a moderate relationship between Information Quality and Attitude Change. This result is consistent with the interview results conducted with informant 2, who stated that: The information shared is useful information that can improve the understanding of young people and change individual behavior to care about the business environment. The importance of quality information motivates every individual to obtain the necessary information. Quality information will certainly benefit individuals. Although young people sometimes haven't considered or are interested in starting a business, the results of observations conducted by the researcher thru the @okoce.indonesia account show that this account actively shares information thru various Instagram features such as Reels, Posts, Collab Posts, Reposts, and Highlight Stories. It is hoped that sharing information through these various features will make it easier for followers to obtain information about environmental business care, especially for MSMEs.

Multiple Correlation Test

Table 8: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Change Statistics						
			Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.665 ^a	.479	.312	1.00317	.326	19.017	2	97	<.001

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2025)

Predictors: (Constant): Social Media Usage; Information Quality Source: Processed Researcher Data, 2025

Based on the table above, the coefficient value (R) is 0.679 and R Square is 0.479 or 47.9%. The remaining 52.1% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. The correlation coefficient has a positive relationship with a strong degree of association, as it falls within the 0.40-0.599 interval, indicating a strong relationship. This indicates a strong positive relationship between Social Media Usage and Information Quality and Attitude Change toward Caring for the Business Environment.

Multiple Regression Test

a. Table 9: Results of the Multiple Regression Test Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	14.329	2.159		3.222	.001
	Penggunaan Media Sosial	.477	.327	.301	3.763	.001
	Kualitas Informasi	.453	.249	.328	3.532	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Behavior Change

Source: Processed Researcher Data, 2025

Based on the table above, the results of the calculation of the independent variables in this study can be arranged with the following model: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$ $Y = 14.329 + 0.477X_1 + 0.453X_2$ The results of the multiple regression test between variables X1: Social Media Usage and X2: Information Quality on Variable Y: Behavior Change can be summarized as follows: a. If the variables Social Media Usage and Information Quality are considered constant, the value of the Behavior Change variable is

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

14.329 units. b. If the value of Social Media Usage increases by one unit and the value of Information Quality is considered constant, the value of Behavior Change increases by 0.477 units. c. If the value of Information Quality increases by one unit and the value of Social Media Usage is constant, the value of Behavior Change will increase by 0.453 units.

T-Test

The partial test (T-test) aims to assess the individual influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, while controlling for other variables. Partial hypotheses are formulated based on strong theory to ensure research validity (Syarifuddin & Saudi, 2022).

Based on the coefficient table above, the value for variable X1: Social Media Usage is t-count 3.763 with a sig value < 0.001. This value is obtained from results where the sig value is less than 0.05 and the t-count is greater than the t-table (1.985). Therefore, there is a significant partial effect of the Social Media Usage variable on Behavior Change. Based on the coefficient table above, the value for variable X2: Information Quality is t-count 3.532 with a sig value < 0.001. This value is obtained from results where the sig value is less than 0.05 and the t-count is greater than the t-table (1.985). Therefore, there is a significant partial effect of the Information Quality variable on Environmental and Business Care Behavior Change, especially for MSMEs.

F-Test

Table. 10: F Test Result

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.338	2	20.125	10.237	<.001 ^b
	Residual	37.129	97	1.229		
	Total	41.893	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Behavior Change

b. Predictors: (Constant): Social Media Usage; Information Quality

Source: Processed Researcher Data, 2025

F table: $(k; n-k) = (2; 100-2) = (2; 98) = 3.09$ Based on the table, the significance level of the F-test results shows an F-calculated value of 10.237 and a Sig value <.001. The value obtained from the data processing test results indicates that the Sig value is < 0.001 or $10.237 (F\text{-calculated}) > 3.09 (F\text{-table})$. Therefore, there is a positive and significant simultaneous influence between the variables of Social Media Usage and Information Quality on Attitude Change.

DISCUSSION

This study uses the Uses and Gratification theory, which explains how audiences actively choose media to meet their various needs and find satisfaction in seeking quality information from various media they believe are capable of providing information satisfaction. In this study, the media used is Instagram. Instagram, through the account @okoce.indonesia, is considered capable of providing various information needs regarding environmental awareness and business care, especially for MSMEs, particularly for young people.

This is reinforced by Informant 1, who stated: "I actively seek the information I need. The @okoce.indonesia account is one of the accounts I often follow because it shares information about environmental care, especially for businesses, particularly MSMEs. As we all know, Indonesia is currently focused on improving MSMEs. Business information is often overlooked by young people, but through the posts on this account, they are encouraged to actively participate in various activities. This @okoce.indonesia account often posts reels and short videos about various activities they've done to share knowledge and experiences.

- As for the assumptions of the Uses and Gratification Theory related to the results of interviews with informants in this study, they are as follows: 1. Followers receive quality information about the business environment, especially MSMEs, through the Instagram account @okoce.indonesia. According to the Uses and Gratification Theory, followers receive information through text messages, images, or videos in advertisements provided on the Instagram account @okoce.indonesia. This is supported by Informant 1, who stated that: "The @okoce.indonesia account regularly provides information about activities related to caring for the business environment, especially for MSMEs, to educate the public, particularly young people, about business. The posts shared are usually educational videos and posters. From the observations made by the researcher, the posts made by the @okoce.indonesia account are shared regularly with attractive titles and message quality aimed at reaching young people to care about the business environment. However, from the observations made by the researcher, not many of the account's followers respond to each post shared." It appears that the younger generation is not yet interested in the business environment and MSMEs. Some of the posts the researcher selected include:

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

Table 11: Observation Results on Information Quality @okoce.indonesia

Content	Explanation
<p>Post content: "Next step BELAJAR KEWIRAUSAHAAN BARENG ADIK-ADIK KAMPUNG PEMULUNG". Includes QR code and contact info for BSI.</p>	<p>From that post, there were 17 likes and 1 repost about "Learning Entrepreneurship Together with the Scavenger Village Children." This post encourages followers to actively participate in learning entrepreneurship with the scavenger children, so they can both understand the concept of entrepreneurship.</p>
<p>Post content: "4 KESALAHAN UMKM yang bikin usaha sulit berkembang".</p>	<p>From that post, 17 people liked the post about Why Endorsements on Social Media Are Important. This post educates about the reasons why MSMEs don't develop and what mistakes they make. This post is important education for all MSMEs to continue growing.</p>
<p>Post content: "4 ALASAN ENDORSEMENT DI MEDIA SOSIAL PENTING!".</p>	<p>From that post, 17 people liked the post about Why Endorsements on Social Media Are Important. This post highlights the importance of social media endorsements for business and MSME growth and recognition by the general public.</p>

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

<p>okoce.indonesia • Lights Follow • Live Your Beautiful Life</p> <p>Alasan Gen Z Lebih Pilih Berbisnis Dibanding Kerja Kantoran</p> <p>23 likes, 1 repost</p> <p>okoce.indonesia Buat banyak Gen Z, bisnis bukan cuma cari cuan... selengkapnya 26 November</p>	<p>From that post, there were 23 likes and 1 repost about the reasons Gen Z prefers to start a business over working in an office. This post opens the minds of young people to become interested in the business environment, especially in areas related to media and technology.</p>
<p>okoce.indonesia • Calvin Harris - Feels (Feat. Pharrell Williams, K...</p> <p>KENAPA INDOMIE NGGAK ADA MATINYA? BEDAH RAHASIA BRAND LONGEVITY BUAT UMKM KAMU!</p> <p>27 likes, 1 comment, 1 repost</p> <p>okoce.indonesia Indomie bukan cuma mie instan tapi bagian dari hidup banyak orang... selengkapnya 25 November</p>	<p>From that post, there were 27 likes, 1 comment, and 1 repost about "Why Indomie Never Dies?" This post educates young people about the importance of a brand for a product, ensuring it remains top of mind for the public and sells well in the market.</p>
<p>okoce.indonesia dan 2 lainnya • Taylor Swift - Style (Taylor's Version)</p> <p>WEBINAR MAKSIMALKAN KARIR SESUAI MINAT & BAKAT</p> <p>30 November 2023 19:00-20:00 WIB via Zoom Meeting</p> <p>Dengan webinar ini kamu bisa:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Menemukan arah karir atau jurusan sesuai minat & bakat Mengoptimalkan potensi diri dengan cara efektif Meningkatkan kepercayaan diri dan kesiapan karir <p>Register Now</p> <p>Benefit:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insightful Knowledge Live Test Penemuan Minat Bakat Exclusive Gift for The Most Active <p>IREN SARAGIH, M.M., M.P. Psikolog</p> <p>28 likes, 3 comments, 5 reposts, 1 share</p> <p>okoce.indonesia BINGUNG PILIH KARIR? ATAU KERJA TAPI NGGAK "KERASA KLIK"?... selengkapnya 24 November</p>	<p>From that post, there were 28 likes, 3 comments, and 5 reposts about Maximizing Your Career Based on Interests and Talents. This post educates young people to recognize their individual interests and talents, which they can then use to maximize their careers.</p>

Source: @okoce.indonesia

- In information searches, the use of video, text, or images can play an important role in quickly informing about a product, especially when time is a crucial factor in the information search. This is supported by Informant 2, who stated: "According to this theory, the use of Instagram media describes the social interaction of followers, which is fundamentally based on the idea that using it to gain satisfaction from information about environmental education and business, and can also be opinions for other followers. This behavioral change is highly subjective, making it difficult to predict the content shared." Regarding the sharing of creative content, the @okoce.indonesia account cannot control the opinions of Instagram media users, but it can create a cooperative discussion space for environmental and business conversations;
- Various information allows the public to be interested in and need that information according to their desires. Uses and Gratification theory in this context studies how people seek and receive information using media. This is supported by Informant 1, who stated: "Seeking and receiving interesting information about the environment and business that is actively shared using various features available on Instagram and linked to news that was trending at the time, such as drinking

The Use of Instagram Media and Information Quality on Changes in Environmental Care Behavior of Young Business Generation (Survey on the @Okoce.Indonesia Account)

from a tumbler to reduce the use of plastic waste." Throwing garbage in the designated places so that it doesn't cause flooding during the rainy season;

5. Uses and Gratification theory examines how communication in the media can influence audiences, both individually and socially. This is supported by informant 2 who stated: "Every post shared by the @okoce.indonesia account creates new knowledge for followers, leading to behavioral changes in environmental care and business concern for the younger generation. This account aims to meet the public's information needs, where Generation Z prefers entrepreneurship over office work. When linked to the results of the correlation test between social media usage and behavioral changes, the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.699. The level of relationship between the two variables falls under strong correlation between social media usage and public behavioral changes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data processing above, the researcher draws the following conclusions:

1. Based on the correlation table, the coefficient value (R) is 0.479 and R Square is 0.479 or 47.9%. This correlation coefficient has a strong and positive relationship, as it falls within the 0.40-0.799 interval with a moderate level of relationship. This indicates a strong positive relationship between Social Media Usage and Information Quality on Attitude Change Toward Environmental Concern;
2. If Social Media Usage and Information Quality are considered constant, the value of Behavior Change is 14.329 units. If Social Media Usage is held constant and Information Quality is held constant, the value of Behavior Change increases by 0.477 units. If Information Quality is held constant and Social Media Usage is held constant, the value of Behavior Change will increase by 0.453 units;
3. Based on the table, the significance results of the F-test show an F-statistic value of 10.237 and a Sig value $<.001$. The values obtained from the data processing test results indicate that $\text{Sig} .001 < 0.05$ or 10.237 (F-statistic) > 3.09 (F-table). Therefore, there is a positive and significant simultaneous influence between the variables of Social Media Usage and Information Quality on Attitude Change.

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